

Synthesis of Coumaron/Coumarinyloxyacetyl Ureas

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Some new N^1 -(2,3-diphenyl coumaron-6-yloxyacetyl)- N^3 -arylureas and N^1 -(4-methyl coumarin-7-yloxyacetyl)- N^3 -arylureas have been synthesised. Six of them reduced the blood sugar upto 24% in rats at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg body weight.

RECENTLY, CS476, N^1 -[4-{2-(2,3-dihydrobenzo(b)furan-7-carboxamido) ethyl benzene sulphonyl]- N^3 -cyclohexylureas has been claimed^{1,2,3}, to be as potent a hypoglycemic agent as Glybenclamide⁴. Also, 4,5,6-trimethyl coumarin derivatives⁵ were found to possess antidiabetic activity comparable to that of chlorpropamide⁶. It was, therefore, considered of interest to synthesise title compounds with a view to study the effect of introducing ureido group in both coumarone (benzofuran) and coumarin nuclei on their hypoglycemic activity.

α -Chloroacetyl-N-arylurea was refluxed with 2,3-diphenyl-6-hydroxy coumarone in dry acetone in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 to give desired coumaronyloxyacetylurea. The same chloroacetylurea was also refluxed with 4-methyl-7-hydroxy coumarin under similar conditions to furnish corresponding coumarinyloxy acetylurea. The compounds, thus synthesised were characterized by their elemental analysis and I.R. spectra.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer in KBr. T.L.C. was carried out using kiesel gel G. coated glass plates of 2 mm thickness.

N^1 -(2,3-Diphenyl Coumaron-6-yloxyacetyl)- N^3 -arylureas :

A mixture of α -chloroacetyl-N-arylurea^{7,8,9} (0.005 mole), 2,3-diphenyl-6-hydroxy coumarone¹⁰ (0.005 mole), dry acetone (50 ml) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (0.01 mole) was refluxed for 18 hours on a steam bath. The reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness and 100 ml of cold water was added to the dry mass with stirring. A solid so obtained was filtered and washed several times with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol. Compounds prepared are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1— N^1 -(2,3-DIPHENYL COUMARON-6-YLOXYACEYL)- N^3 -ARYLUREAS⁺

Compound No.	Ar	M.P. °C
1.	C_6H_5	178
2.	2- $CH_3C_6H_4$	218
3.	3- $CH_3C_6H_4$	233
4.	4- $CH_3C_6H_4$	240
5.	2- $OCH_3C_6H_4$	208
6.	3- $OCH_3C_6H_4$	211
7.	4- $OCH_3C_6H_4$	222
8.	4- $OC_2H_5C_6H_4$	204
9.	2- ClC_6H_4	258
10.	4- ClC_6H_4	280

All compounds analysed well for C, H and N.

⁺ Yields ranged between 45-60%.

Compounds No. 1, 4, 6, 7, 8 and 10 showed characteristic bands at 3150-3250 cm^{-1} (-NH), 1640-1690 cm^{-1} (amide C=O) and 1160-1240 cm^{-1} (Ar-o- CH_2).

N^1 -(4-Methyl Coumarin-7-yloxyacetyl)- N^3 -arylureas :

α -Chloroacetyl-N-arylurea (0.007 mole), 4-methyl-7-hydroxy coumarin¹¹ (0.007 mole), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (0.01 mole) and dry acetone (100 ml) were refluxed for 16 to 18 hours on a steam bath. Thereafter, the mixture was evaporated to complete dryness and water (100 ml) was added to it with shaking. The solid thus separated was filtered, washed several times with cold water and recrystallised from 90% ethanol. Compounds prepared are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2—N¹-(4-METHYL COUMARIN-7-yLOXYACETYL)-N³-ARYLUREAS[†]

Compound No.	Ar	M.P °C
11.	C ₆ H ₅	198
12.	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	224
13.	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	212
14.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	262
15.	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	235
16.	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	218
17.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	214
18.	4-OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	210
19.	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	214
20.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	225

All compounds analysed well for C, H and N.

[†]Yields ranged between 60-70%.

The I. R. spectra of the Compounds No. 12, 14, 16, 17, 18 and 20 showed characteristic bands at 3100-3200 cm⁻¹ (-NH), 1710-1725 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O), 1690-1600 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O) and 1220-1140 cm⁻¹ (Ar-*o*-CH₃).

Pharmacology :

Six of the compounds (No. 4,7,8,14,17 and 18) were examined for their hypoglycemic activity, for which blood samples were drawn from the tail vein of fasted albino rats weighing between 200 and 250 gms and their glucose contents were estimated by Nelson Somogyi method¹². The compounds under test were administered orally at single oral dose of 250 mg/kg body weight. Blood samples were again taken at intervals of 1,2 and 4 hours and their glucose contents were estimated. The average maximum reduction in blood sugar for the above compounds were 24,11,9,13,10 and 7% respectively.

It appears that in both the coumarin and coumarone series the compound with Ar=*p*-Tolyl analogous to that present in a well known antidiabetic drug Tolbutamide had the highest hypoglycemic activity. It is also inferred that the introduction of ureido group in both coumarin and coumarone nuclei did not enhance the hypoglycemic activity to a significant extent.

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